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Research

Effect of Tungsten Content on Corrosion Resistance and Hardness of Aluminum by Electro-less Coating

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Abstract: *Nickle-Tungsten-Phosphorous (Ni-W-P) alloy coating was prepared by electro-less nickel plating on pure aluminum sheet. For activation of aluminum surface, pickling and zinc immersion was carried out. Furthermore, reinforcement and reduction of corrosion potential, copper electroplating was inspected before deposition for better adherence. In this present research work focus on the variation of tungsten content in chemical plating bath for constant plating time. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) was used to observe the surface morphology of the samples. Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) was used to determine the coating composition and thickness of the coating catalyst. Behavior of hardness was measured by Vickers hardness tester techniques while its porosity have been observed by stereoscope. The medium used for corrosion resistance testing was 0.9% sodium chloride (NaCl) with hydrochloric acid (HCl) giving 4-5 pH. The predominant phase in the coating was nickel along with phosphides of nickel and nodules of tungsten content. Coating showed higher hardness and good corrosion resistance as compared to substrate. With increase in tungsten content, hardness increased and spherical size was decreased. Hence, uniform and thick coating was obtained.*

Keywords : *Aluminum surface; Corrosion potential; Tungsten; Electroplating; Hardness*

Introduction:

Aluminum is the leader metal in non-ferrous metallurgy due to its lightness, high strength, suitable for surface treatments, extruded and cast semi products, thermal and electrical conductivity and easy recycling. To avoid pitting corrosion and blackening and to obtain superficial hardness surface treatments of aluminum are necessary[1-3]. Electro-less or autocatalytic plating involves the chemical reducing agent to convert metallic ions into metallic state in the solution. In electro-less plating, substrate acts as cathode and the salt is used as anode. Electric current is passed through salt instead of electrodes and reducing agent provides electrons. Surface cleaning and activation is necessary for deposition and different metals have different methods of cleaning and activation[4]. Electro-less nickel-phosphorus alloy coatings are of great interest now a day due to their successful properties such as high hardness, good corrosion resistance, uniform thickness and good magnetic response. These coatings are considered as functional coatings due to their applications in different industries such as automotive, aerospace, chemical, oil and gas[5].

Electro-less Ni-W-P coating on aluminum substrate is useful coating to avoid pitting corrosion and to increase hardness. It has many applications in different industries such as different types of control valves, engine valves, aluminum blow molds, aluminum pelletizers, bearings, rollers, gears, hydraulics, aluminum fuel filters, components in contact with alcohol, aluminum connectors, spacers and assemblies etc. In electro-less Ni-W-P coating, sodium hypophosphite is used as reducing agent to reduce nickel metal ions. Chemical reduction takes place in this method[6]. Aluminum substrates make a strong oxide layer on its surface which is destroyed in corrosive environment so electro-less Ni-W-P coating is applied to protect aluminum from pitting corrosion. Due to oxide layer, there is poor adhesion between substrate and the required coating. Zincating is the process which enhances the adhesion. In this process thin layer of zinc is applied after activation of the substrate. Thin layer of copper plating may also be done for reinforcement of the coating. In electro-less plating, firstly nucleation sites (activation sites) are formed which are main center to start and to continue the coating. When work piece is immersed into the solution, islands start to form around the nucleation sites and then these sites increase in size and merge in each other with passage of time. Thus, a dense and uniform coating is formed and this phenomenon is time dependent. Nucleation sites also change the direction of the crystals deposited on the substrate with the help of ions supplied from the solution. Properties of the deposit such as morphology, porosities, thermal stresses etc. are changed by change of direction of crystals[7-9].

The purpose of the present study is to obtain an effective coating with increased corrosion resistance in corrosive environment. Electro-less Ni-W-P coating is directly carried out on pure aluminum and effect of bath temperature on crystal structure, deposition rate; surface morphology, chemical composition and corrosion resistance of Ni-W-P plated aluminum are observed.

Aluminum (Al) substrates of 99.5% purity, $1 \times 2 \text{cm}^2$, were cut in form of strips. Ni-W-P deposit was obtained from different chemicals such as sodium tungstate, sodium hypophosphite, and nickel sulfate are the materials used for experimental work.

Pickling and degreasing is followed in this work because it is effective for the adhesion of coatings. Oxide layer was removed from the sample by washing with detergent followed by pickled in a solution of nitric acid and hydrofluoric acid ($\text{HNO}_3 + \text{HF}$, 3:1) for 2min. The washed and surface clean samples was then used for coating. To remove oxide layer, firstly zinc coating was done on aluminum substrate for 10sec at 30°C . For reinforcement of Ni-W-P coating, copper electroplating was through above zinc coating at 4.5A of current upon 60°C . The change in the physiochemical properties of aluminum, Ni-W-P alloy coating is then employed above copper electroplating. Chemical composition of Ni-W-P coating is given below in table 1.

Table 1. Bath Composition of Electro-less Ni-W-P Coating

Constituent	Value (g/l)	Parameter	Value
Nickel Sulphate(NiSO_4)	7	Temperature	90 C
Sodium Citerate(NaC_2H_7)	40	PH	8.2
Sodium Hypo-phosphite(NaH_2PO_2)	10	Immersion time	1 hr
Sodium Tungstate (Na_2WO_4)	5/7/9/11	Agitation	Mechanical

The hardness of as received and coated samples were determined by Micro-Vickers hardness machine having 490.3mN load. Potentiostat was used for corrosion test and cyclic polarization test was performed to analyze pitting corrosion as aluminum suffers from pitting corrosion. For that analysis, electrolyte was made in 1000ml distilled water containing 0.9% NaCl with HCl giving 4-5 PH. Electrolyte in another beaker was made with graphite electrode and standard electrode. Then samples were tested to get corrosion curves. The micrographs of coated specimens were carried out on scanning electron microscope (SEM) (S-3000N) at different magnifications such as 250X, 370X, 500X, 1000X, 3000X, 7000X and 10000X to identified different modes of surfaces.

The SEM results of electro-less nickel alloy coating with secondary zinc and copper treatment shows that the surface topography of the deposit contains spherical nodular structure with very fine and compact grains. The surface morphology of the coating is shown in figure 1. These results clearly indicates that nodular size decreases with increase in tungsten content which indicates that deposit is adherent. Electro-less Ni-P-W deposition is a time dependent nucleation and growth phenomena for an adherent coating. Firstly, after nucleation, the Ni-P alloy grains grow into spherical nodules. Secondly, the number of nucleating sites increases with time, creating more nodules. With increase in plating time, deposition on surface occurs and then these new deposited Ni-P alloy particles become new nucleation center to deposit further particles. So, deposition rate of phosphorus and tungsten particles increases until surface is completely covered with coating. The as-formed coating has the catalytic activity required for the autocatalytic reaction, and this promoted the nucleation and growth of the coating in the transverse direction. Fig.1 shows micrographs of Ni-W-P coating with 7, 9 and 11 g/l Na_2WO_4 compositions at magnification of 7000X.

Fig 1 Micrographs of Ni-W-P coating with 7, 9 and 11 g/l W compositions at magnification of 7000X

Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) was done to detect energy spectrum as shown in figure 2. It is investigated that the surface of the sample contains elements of Ni, W, P, Cu and Zn because the sample is subjected to zinc and copper treatment before electro-less Ni-W-P plating. The contents of the coating increase with increase in time but content of zinc

and copper disappear gradually after some time because nickel, tungsten, phosphorus particles are mainly deposited on zinc and copper coating. Figure 2 illustrates the composition spectrums of different concentrations of Na_2WO_4 such as 7, 9 and 11%.

Fig.2 Composition spectrums of concentrations of W with 7%, 9% and 11%

The cyclic polarization curve of bare aluminum and coated samples with different concentration of tungsten was observed as shown in Figure 3. Cyclic Polarization test tells about probability of pitting corrosion, breakdown potential (Pitting Potential) and protection potential. According to the graph given below, in pure aluminum no loop is made which means that there is severe pitting corrosion. As tungsten content is increased, a hysteresis loop is made but loop is not closed which means that there is some pitting corrosion. The area of loop tells about the probability of pitting corrosion. As further tungsten content is increased, reverse scan becomes close to forward scan showing less pitting corrosion and when more tungsten content is increased then loop becomes close which indicates protection potential which means that coating is protected.

In curves in figure 3 suggests that samples are firstly cathodically polarized where hydrogen evolution occurs and then anodically polarized where metal dissolution occurs. This scan is called forward scan. After that a potential is given to take metal ions from solution which is called reverse scan. When forward scan cut the reverse scan then protection potential is reported. After 60 minutes, coating becomes saturated with improved coverage and thickness.

Fig.3 Micrographs with 0, 7, 9 and 11 g/l W

Corrosion potential and corrosion current shows in increasing trend by adding intermediate copper and zinc layers corrosion potential is increased which indicates better adherence between coating and substrate. Copper layer is introduced because it has lower difference of coefficient of thermal expansion with Ni-W-P coating and it also makes good adhesion with zinc. Hence, corrosion resistance is increased by introducing copper layer.

The hardness of Ni-W-P coating increases with increase in concentration of tungsten content and time as shown in Figure.4 given below. Due to increase in the concentration of tungsten the spherical size decrease and particle become smaller due to which hardness increases.

Fig. 4. Vickers hardness by increasing the percentage of W in the Ni-W-P coatings

Figure 5 shows that there is less porosity in the coating. These micrographs have 0, 7, 9, and 11g/l Na_2WO_4 respectively.

Fig.5 Porosity with 0, 7, 9 and 11g/l W

4. Conclusions

After the electroless plating for a fixed time, the Ni-W-P particles deposited on the surface of the sample were seen to increase with the plating time. The particles begin to accumulate, grow, fuse, and have a nodular structure on the surface. During the initial stage of electroless nickel plating, nickel-phosphorus particles were deposited near the Cu particles and between the Cu particles. Zincating process was used for activation of surface and to get fine nodules of the coating. Zinc and copper layers were plated before Ni-W-P coating for better adhesion.

Hardness was increased with the increase in tungsten content and plating time which can be used to replace some metals and save resources. With increase in plating time, thickness of the coating was increased and porosity was decreased. Atomic binding force against plastic deformation was increased by co-deposition of tungsten so that the hardness of the deposits of Ni-W-P was higher than the Ni-P deposits and substrate. Thus, the properties of electroless Ni-P coatings were enhanced by co-deposition with tungsten. Electroless Ni-P-W plating exhibited a nodular surface profile. Corrosion studies indicated that as composition of sodium tungstate increases, coating becomes nobler. As a result, the bonding of Ni-W-P deposit and aluminium substrate is in good condition.

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